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SWOT Analysis of Urban Development on Kolonnawa Urban Council, Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

Changes in land use and land cover are a result of urban growth. Human activity has a vital role in city development since it helps to increase people's living standards, property values, accessibility, and safety. This study looked into the importance of legal procedures in accordance with the country's long-term development goals. It was also used to reveal the area's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and risks to the environment and people due to urban development. The study gathered data from both primary and secondary sources. The SWOT analysis was used to highlight the implications of urban growth in the research area. Maps analysis has been done using Geographic Information Systems (GIS). The statistical data on unauthorized filling was analyzed using Microsoft Excel. The findings show that, rather than being a source of strength and opportunity, urban expansion is also a source of weakness and risks. Threats to natural resources and humans, in particular, are disproportionately significant. Due to land demand, 62% of the land has been developed, jeopardizing the available marsh and paddy area. The growth of Kolonnawa urban council, which is located below mean sea level (MSL), causes flooding in the area every year. Based on a 50 year flood inundation, the grama niladari divisions of Wadulla, Orugodawatta, Meethotamulla, Gajabapura, Wijayapura, and Salamulla have been declared as high impacted locations.

Keywords: Urban development, SWOT analysis, GIS, Land demand, MSL

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban development improves the land with high-rise buildings, leisure parks, walking paths, grounds, and roads. It has been started with the industrial revolution (Arku, Yeboah and Nyantakyi-Frimpong, 2016). Urban development led to a change in land cover type from permeable soil to artificially impermeable (Shao *et al.*, 2019). The built surface can change the natural hydrological conditions by increasing the volume and the rate of surface runoff and reducing the recharge and base flow of the groundwater (Harbor, 2007). This eventually led to more extensive and more frequent flooding. Urban development should follow planning for sustainable development to overcome social and environmental issues that occur through the development (Djordjević *et al.*, 2011).

The development of cities changes the land use patterns' physical characteristics. Improper urban development cause threats as providing goods and services equally, air pollution which forces on human health, health risk due to a large amount of waste generation (Boadi *et al.*, 2005). Mainly it can be rise environmental issues such as loss of habitat for animals and birds, flooding, loss of vegetation cover, and water pollution (Cutter, 2008). The water pollution results reduction in water quality within the urban area (Nishanthi *et al.*, 2021).

The of contamination of polluted water may cause cancer in human beings through epigenetical modification pathway (R Dushanan *et al.*, 2020; Ramachandren Dushanan *et al.*, 2020). As per the sustainable development goal adopted by the united nation in 2015, the 11th goal, "sustainable cities and communities," is used to consider proper urban planning for sustainable development (Kutty *et al.*, 2020). Increasing population and migration force rapid development of cities. At present, more than half of the people in the world live in cities, and it is assumed in 2050, two-third of people will live in cities (Berardi, 2017). Sustainable development is possible to achieve with the planning of building structure and proper management of urban space. Sustainable development considers the environment and ecosystem services provided for quality life for people and the earth itself (Howarth and Farber, 2002). Diantiny, 2020; Al Fataa, 2021; Kayya, 2021; Nisheeth, 2020).

Sri Lanka is a developing country with 22 million people. The land extent of the country is 65,610 square kilometers, and the population density is 325 people per square kilometer (Sarvananthan, 2004). The governing boundary determines the urban status of Sri Lanka as a municipal council or urban council. According to the Urban Development Authority act of Sri Lanka, several areas other than these have also been declared as urban development areas (Kuruppu *et al.*, 2016). It is not about the administrative status of local authorities but the availability of urban facilities and the characteristics of urban places. More is achieving kinds of lifestyle changes from country to the city. Population growth causes improper development of land, which is not permitted for construction (Kates, 2014). From the 1970s to the 1980s, the nearest urban centers surrounding Colombo city experienced rapid growth. High urbanized centers can currently be seen in freshly constructed areas outside of Colombo (Dutt and Noble, 2004). Rural land uses are swiftly changed into urban activities throughout this period. The country's urbanization rate is very high in the Colombo metropolitan region. Colombo and its suburbs are the commercial and administrative capital and the first, second, third, and fourth urban centers in the national urban hierarchy (Dutt and Noble, 2004).

Urban development should consider the landscape for improvement and construction of the land. Kolonnawa urban council area is located below than mean sea level (Kularatne, 2014). The area has low land as marsh, barren, muddy lands, ovita, deniya, asliyadda, and paddy fields.

In Kolonnawa, wastewater and stormwater drainage have been an issue because most recovered low-lying lands lack a suitable gradient for natural drainage. According to the urban council, roughly 80% of the low-lying regions have been reclaimed for housing and other development purposes at various times. Drainage canals have also been filled as part of the land reclamation operation. Several studies have been done about Kolonnawa area for project purposes. But the analysis used to show the importance of legal procedure and government authorities' concern for proper land development based on sustainable development goals of the country. It is also used to expose the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats caused to the environment and humans in the area.

2. STUDY AREA

Figure 1. Location map of Kolonnawa urban council

The city of Kolonnawa is located on the eastern border of the Colombo city. The north, east, south and west of the Kolonnawa urban council is covered by Kelani River, Kotikawatta-Mulleriyawa pradeshiya sabha, Kotte municipal council and Colombo municipal council, respectively. The extent of the area is 5.3 square kilometers. Kolonnawa is a multi-ethnic community with Sinhalese, Sri Lankan Tamils, Indian Tamils, Sri Lankan Muslims, and others, where people coexist in peace and harmony. It is a flood plain of Kelani River, and the area is below than mean sea level. The Harward flood bund was used to protect the area from flood

hazards to Colombo city constructed in 1935. The north of the bund is an unprotected area, and development is not allowed, and the south of the Bund is a protected area, and development is allowed. The protected area included low-lying land thus the part of the area have development restriction. The study area shown in Figure 1.

Activity Path for Issuing Recommendation to Develop Lands

Figure 2. Activity path to obtain approval for land development

3. LEGAL FRAMEWORK

As per the Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation Act 15 of 1968 as amended by act no 54 of 1984 and act no 35 of 2006, the corporation has the authority to grant permission for the public to fill low land subjected to the provision of stormwater drainage within the declared area. The declared provinces of the country are Western, Southern, Uva, Central, Sabaragamuwa, and Northwest

The filling conducting without approval from relevant authority will identify as unauthorized landfilling. The Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation has the authority to stop such illicit filling of low land which cause drainage issue and natural hazard such as a flood. As well as to develop a low land, approval should obtain from the Central Environmental Authority, Urban Development Authority, the Department of Agrarian Development, and the Local Authority of the area. These are the authorities often used to obtain development approval.

Further, it may need to get permission from authorities that are not listed above. It will be determined by the location of the land which is planning for development. The Figure 2 illustrates the procedures that should follow to obtain approval for low land development.

4. METHODOLOGY

The data is obtained from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data is gathered through interviews, observations, and conversations with experts. From 2016 to 2020, the Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation gathered information that resulted in the compilation of statistics on the unlawful filling of areas. Data on the flood hazard was acquired from the Survey Department of Sri Lanka and the Disaster Management Center. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have been used to produce maps and do map analysis. Microsoft Excel was used to analyze the statistical data on unauthorized filling.

The SWOT analysis aids in the development of a strategic agenda by identifying critical concerns that must be prioritized in order to advance a viable and sustainable strategy to urban resource management (Elavarasan *et al.*, 2021). The analysis is used to list out the impact of urban development (Berte and Panagopoulos, 2014). It is a good technique for organizing information obtained during the study period to discuss, prioritize, and agree on the city's difficulties (Khatri and Metri, 2016).

A SWOT analysis identifies and categorizes the city's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats due to development (Zhang, 2012).

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Population growth and land demand are the reasons to the infrastructure changes of the Kolonnawa urban council. It has an impact on the area's land use and land cover. Built area, paddy land, marshes, highways, and hydrology are the land utilization pattern of the area. The 2021 Kolonnawa urban council land use map (Figure 3) generated by the examiner shows that 72% of the land has already been turned to development space, including primary and secondary roads (Table 1).

Table 1. Land Use Patter of Kolonnawa urban council.

Landuse pattern of Kolonnawa	The extent of the area (km ²)	Percentage (%)
Built area	2.60	62
Paddy land	0.86	12
Marshes	0.80	11
Hydrology	0.16	03
Major and minor roads	0.61	10

Figure 3. Land Use Map of Kolonnawa urban council

As per the land use pattern of the Kolonnawa urban council the SWOT analysis has been used to list the strength, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of urban development.

5. 1. Strength

The strength of the study area recorded as that the location of the Kolonnawa has built up for the economic purpose, and it used to develop as the back yard of Colombo city due to its location and transportation facilities for the utilization of oil storage place, container yard, electricity substation, and warehouse. Kolonnawa is strategically essential for wholesale distribution of commodities due to its location to the east of Baseline road and its proximity to the Kandy road and low-level road to Avissawella.

Its economy is inextricably linked to the activities of the city of Colombo and is mainly dependent on the city's activity pattern. The town also houses a significant section of Colombo's working population. The surface is covered with green patches as marshes and paddy fields. And it is rich in the hydrological network. The example photographs of available marshland and water resources of Kolonnawa urban council are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Natural resources of Kolonnawa urban council. (a) Mangroos of Kolonnawa Marshland, (b) Swamps and Mangroos of Marshland at Kuruniyawatta, (c) Water body (Selalihini Canal) of Kolonnawa urban council and (d) Mangroos of Kolonnawa Marshland at Salamulla.

5. 2. Weakness

The urban development changes the physical form and land use patterns may be locked for several generations, leading to unsustainable expansion. The poor families live in Kolonnawa city have encroached on the land for their settlement purpose. This has led to many illegal settlements in the low-lying areas of Kolonnawa and vulnerable to flooding. Table 2 shows non-approved filling without drainage planning which was not recorded from Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation. The Figure 5 shows the lowland filling, observed during the field visit to Kolonnawa urban council.

Figure 5. Lowland filling at Kolonnawa urban council. (a) Unauthorized Filling of land with canal reservation at Sedawatta grama niladari division, (b) Unauthorized land filling for development at Wijayabapura, (c) Unauthorized land filling for development at Kolonnawa grama niladari division and (d) Unauthorized land filling for development at Orugodawatta grama niladari division.

Vehicle traffic was also recognized as a vulnerability. The area's traffic is becoming increasingly congested as a result of urban growth. The primary road network that passes through Kolonnawa is comprised of Baseline road and Avissawella road. Kolonnawa's subregional and city roads include Kolonnawa road, Meethotamulla road, Perera Avenue,

Fraser road, Nagahamulla road, Ranasingha road, Wijaya road, Angoda road, Rathnavalie road, and Kumaradasa road. It has a road network that connects all of the cities surrounding Sri Jayawardenapura. The government sector employees who work in the administrative capital rely on this road for mobility. Thus it causes severe traffic in the area.

Table 2. Non approved landfilling.

Year	Number of Location
2016	13
2017	08
2018	07
2019	07
2020	06

Furthermore, topography and geomorphic characteristics were not taken into account in the construction of the drainage network. The drainage network was restricted to specific regions, and the existing culvert lacked enough drainage capacity. Solid waste management is in disarray. Environmental concerns arise due to a lack of solid waste management in conjunction with a growing population (Nishanthi and Kaleel, 2021).

5. 3. Opportunity

With its resources and facilities, the city of Kolonnawa attracted investors. The town has built high-rise apartments, and the roads have been improved to improve transportation. Kolonnawa's urban development facilitates a variety of sectors that contribute to the country's economic growth. The industries are United Motors vehicle repair workshop, food granaries, textiles, Kelanitissa electricity substation, petroleum oil storage installations, warehousing complex, several saw mills, timber depots, and Container yard. These are the key industries that contribute to the area's economic activity, and the area's industrial development provides job opportunities for the general people in and around Kolonnawa.

The foundation for several projects suggested for Kolonnawa urban council is the area's urban development. Sanhinda Sevana, a housing project for low-income families in Kolonnawa, was completed in 2020. A total of 240 housing units were built as part of the project. This house was designed for low-income persons who reside in homes with fewer than 200 square feet.

The goal of the Kolonnawa canal diversion program was to develop the Kitanpahuwa canal, which passes through the Kolonnawa basin, and connects it to the Colombo basin through a closed construction. The Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation recommended various projects to improve the area's stormwater drainage. It was divided into three categories: short-term, medium-term, and long-term activities.

Short-term processes are the recovery of discharge and transportation capacity of the existing channel system through surface cleaning, countertop cleaning, bridges, and culvert cleaning.

Medium-term proposals are rehabilitation of canal system to increase outfall, conveyance, and retention capacities to an acceptable level under gravity flow at the water level of minor floods in Kelani River and relocation of utility lines that obstruct the water flow at bridges and culverts.

Long-term plans are establishing pump stations at two outfalls of the kittampahuwa canal and salalihini mawatha canal to cope with the minor flood situations of Kelani River and restore existing available water retention areas, and wise use them. Establish a canal maintenance unit in the local authority. Regulate future developments with rules and regulations stipulated by Sri Lanka Land Development Corporation and Urban Development Authority

5. 4. Threats

Unplanned urban development cause threats to the environment. Most parts of the Kolonnawa is in the Kelani River’s drainage basin. With the building of the current flood protection barrier by the Irrigation Department in 1935, a significant portion of the urban council area was protected from Kelani river floods. It allows for some degree of urbanization. However, it retained numerous low lands as flood retention zones, prone to floods after heavy rains.

The Kolonnawa drainage basin has grown increasingly urbanized during the previous four decades. In this scenario, the low elevation region of the Kolonnawa basin flooding every year.

The drainage basin of the area can be defined as mentioned in Table 3.

Table 3. Elevation variation of Kolonnawa urban council.

Mean Sea Level (MSL) (m)	Area
0.5 – 1.0	Low land marsh areas
1.0 – 1.5	Low lands with shanties
1.5 – 2.5	Flood prone areas with small size households
Above 2.5	Except for a very severe river flood, there is no significant flood danger in this area.

Due to highly changing hydrological processes in urban areas, watersheds are more susceptible to flooding. Most urban spaces are waterproof, such as paved roads, patios, and concrete buildings. Therefore, infiltration is reduced, and runoff is rapid. Thus, the overflowing of the Kelani River and rainfall over a period of time caused flooding in the Kolonnawa area.

The Table 4 shows the classification of flood hazard occurs in the Kolonnawa urban council.

Table 4. Flood hazard classification of Kolonnawa patios.

No.	Types	Definition
1	Floods in Kolonnawa as a result of extremely high flows in the Kelani river,	This situation can develop when there is a lot of rain in the central mountains of Sri Lanka. The Kolonnawa basin inundates as a result of the Sedawatte – Ambatale road overtopping. This situation may arise without rainfall at Kolonnawa.
2	Flooding at Kolonnawa caused by canal overflow during high Kelani river flow.	The bunds may not be breached in this case, but their own water still floods the region since gravity drainage to the Kelani river is not conceivable.
3	Flooding at Kolonnawa caused by canal overflow during low Kelani river flow	This situation develops due to canal conveyance inadequacies and canal obstructions caused by inadequate maintenance and encroachment of canal reservations.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 6. Flood inundation occurred in Kolonnawa urban council. (a) Flood inundation of Kolonnawa main road, (b) Flood inundation of Orugodawatta road, (c) Flood inundation of Angoda road, (d) Flood inundation of developed area in Meethotamulla.

As per the elevation of the Kolonnawa urban council, it is frequently affected by flood hazards. In the last five years, Kolonnawa metropolitan area influenced by all minor, medium, and significant floods. The major flood experienced by the area can be listed as floods on May 2016, May 2017, and March 2021. Figure 6 shows the flood inundated areas of Kolonnawa UC on 21st of March, 2021.

Especially in 2016, due to storm "Ronu", which caused heavy rains in almost all parts of Sri Lanka. In particular, the rainfall of Colombo area exceeded 200 mm. Rainfall in the upper and lower parts of the Kelani River was relatively heavy, and many regions in the lower Kelani River were affected by the disasters. According to the Kolonnawa Division Secretariat (DSD) statistics, in the 13 grama niladhari division of the Kolonnawa urban council, 43591 people from 9111 families were affected. Thus the urban development threatens both the nature and the humans of the area.

According to the 50 year worst flood inundation map analysis (Figure 7), 24.65 square kilometers of Colombo district have been identified as high flood prone areas. The Kolonnawa urban council was flooded to the extent of 1.51 square kilometers. According to the study, 28% of the Kolonnawa urban area has been identified as the most flood prone area.

Figure 7. 50 years worst flood inundation map of Kolonnawa UC

The Kolonnawa urban area is becoming increasingly vulnerable to floods due to increasing physical risk associated with environmental changes and rapid land use change and urbanization. Floods are caused by human actions such as uncontrolled land use or haphazard development, as well as hydro-meteorological circumstances. As per the map, the grama niladari areas of Wadulla, Orugodawatta, Meethotamulla, Gajabapura, Wijayapura, and Salamulla have been designated as high impacted areas based on a 50 year flood inundation analysis. The area's land use map was used to identify low lands near the Heen Ela canal, with marshes, paddy lands, and built-up areas. The maps depict the dangers of unplanned development. According to the land use map, the available paddy is 12%, and marshland is 11%. The threat to the Kolonnawa urban council's vegetative patch can be seen in the land extent of built areas. Because of the high demand for land in the area, marsh and paddy land are likely to creep for development purposes. As well as the waste dumping on water path cause water pollution. To conserve the available environment, it is compulsory to incorporate the development with urban planning.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The city council of Kolonnawa is the principal city in the district of Colombo. The region is utilized to develop for human needs depending on population increase. According to the research analysis, the region was rich in natural resources, including green flora. Without good design, the region has begun to develop. Due to the development, the city has strength and opportunities. The main strength is the natural resources of the area and opportunities' are project proposals for further development of the town. But the development has weaknesses and threats for both humans and nature. The research outcome shows that the environmental and human threat is higher than the positive factors due to the development. The landscape of the area is defined by roughly 25% high land and 75% low-lying regions, both of which have been filled in the previous two to three decades. In the past, these low-lying regions constituted Kolonnawa's marshes and water bodies, which helped sustain the inhabitants and the environment. In terms of essential utilities, there is a difference between the orderly development of highland populated by the middle class and the low-income communities in low-lying locations. Poor sanitary conditions in high-density, low-income settlements with no basic facilities contribute to the development of infectious illnesses, a severe concern in the town. Man-made activities such as the establishment of polluting industries, unregulated and excessive landfilling, and the establishment of human settlements have severely harmed the city's environment, including internal water bodies, wetlands, canal and drainage networks, river embankments, natural vegetation, and so on. Pollution of inland water bodies and wetlands has happened as a result of this. Aside from corruption, numerous homes and other structures are at risk of floods. Thus, it is essential to consider sustainable development considering natural resources, ecosystem services, drainage, water supply, waste management, disaster management, and proper plans and legal regulation.

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